

GREEN SYNTHESIS OF ANTIMICROBIAL SILVER NANOPARTICLES FROM GREEN TEA LEAF, GINGER, GARLIC, AND CAPSICUM EXTRACTS FOR APPLICATION IN FOOD PRESERVATION

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ABSTRACT

Silver nanoparticles were green synthesized using aqueous extracts of ginger, garlic, capsicum, green tea leaves, and their combinations, with successful formation confirmed by characteristic surface plasmon resonance peaks in UV–Visible spectroscopy. Antimicrobial activity was extract-dependent, with garlic-mediated AgNPs showing strong inhibition against *Escherichia coli*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, and *Salmonella Typhi*, ginger-mediated AgNPs being effective against *Bacillus cereus*, and the ginger–capsicum combination exhibiting the highest overall efficacy among the combinations synthesized. Incorporation of AgNPs into coatings and gelatin films significantly enhanced the shelf life of fresh-cut apple and pineapple by delaying browning, fungal growth, and spoilage while preserving texture and appearance, with ginger and ginger–capsicum AgNP formulations performing best. Film characterization indicated that AgNP incorporation influenced

thickness, swelling, and moisture content, affecting barrier properties, demonstrating the potential of plant-mediated AgNP-based coatings and films as ecofriendly fruit preservation systems.

KEYWORDS: AgNP, ginger, garlic, capsicum, tea, ginger AgNP, garlic AgNP, gin-cap AgNP, gelatin nanocomposite film, CMC based coatings, grapes, pineapple, apple.

1] INTRODUCTION

Nanotechnology is an interdisciplinary field involving the use of materials with dimensions of 1–100 nm, where size reduction leads to distinct physical and chemical properties compared to bulk materials. Nanoparticles exhibit a high surface area to volume ratio, resulting in enhanced reactivity, catalytic activity, mass transfer, and unique optical, mechanical, magnetic, and quantum effects. These characteristics contribute to improved solubility, bioavailability, diffusivity, and overall functional performance, enabling nanomaterials to be systematically classified based on their size, structure, and properties. (Bajpai *et al.*, 2018)

Nanoparticles, also known as ultrafine particles, are materials with dimensions ranging from 1 to 100 nm. They can be classified based on size, shape, dimensionality, and composition, with zero-dimensional nanoparticles having all dimensions confined to a single point. Nanoparticles exhibit diverse morphologies such as spherical, cylindrical, tubular, spiral, and irregular forms, and are broadly categorized into organic and inorganic types based on their material composition. (Altammar *et al.*, 2023)

Silver is widely recognized for its potent antibacterial properties. Silver is traditionally used in nitrate form for antimicrobial purposes; however, silver nanoparticles provide a much larger reactive surface area, enhancing microbial exposure. AgNPs larger than 10 nm act mainly through electrostatic interaction with negatively charged bacterial membranes, while smaller AgNPs (<10 nm) can enter cells and release Ag⁺ ions intracellularly. Additionally, AgNPs induce antimicrobial effects by disrupting gene expression, damaging mitochondrial function, destabilizing cell membranes, and generating reactive oxygen species (Tashi *et al.*, 2016).

Green synthesis involves the use of plant extracts, where plant derived secondary metabolites act as reducing and stabilizing agents to produce nanoparticles with uniform size, good stability, and without the generation of toxic by-products (Vishwanath *et al.*, 2021).

Ginger is the rhizome of *Zingiber officinale* and is valued for its broad health benefits, including antimicrobial, antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, and anticancer activities. These properties are mainly attributed to phenolic compounds such as gingerols and shogaols, with 6-gingerol being the major constituent in fresh ginger, while 6-shogaol increases upon heating or drying and becomes predominant at high temperatures. Ginger has a broad

metabolites range that can lead to fast reduction of metal ions than microbes, hence they are a suitable source for nanoparticle preparation. Nanoparticles synthesized using ginger extract have been found to be effective against *Salmonella enterica*, *S. aureus*, *E. coli* (Jassim *et al.*, 2023).

Garlic is the bulb of *Allium sativum* and contains sulfur-rich volatile compounds. Upon crushing, the enzyme alliinase converts the odorless amino acid alliin into allicin, an organosulfur compound responsible for garlic's characteristic odor and its antimicrobial activity (El-Saber Batiha *et al.*, 2020). Garlic extract incorporated silver nanoparticles synthesized at 60-65°C have shown to have antimicrobial activity against *Candida albicans*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *Micrococcus sp*, *Klebsiella*, *Proteus*, *Clostridium*, *Mycobacterium* and *Helicobacter* species. (Shafea *et al.*, 2021; Youssef *et al.*, 2021).

Capsicum annum fruits are rich in phenolic compounds, flavonoids, and the bioactive molecule capsaicin, which contribute to their antioxidant and antimicrobial properties (Chan *et al.*, 2020; Ivan *et al.*, 2024). Silver nanoparticles synthesized using *C. annum* extracts have shown strong antimicrobial activity against *Micrococcus luteus*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Escherichia coli*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *Pseudomonas fluorescens*, *Bacillus subtilis*, *Candida albicans*, *Rhizopus oryzae*, *Aspergillus niger*, *Aspergillus parasiticus*, and *Aspergillus flavus*, producing larger zones of inhibition than plant extracts alone (Kalynovskyi *et al.*, 2023; Bibi *et al.*, 2024).

Green tea leaves contain catechins and hydroxyl-rich flavonoids that act as efficient electron donors, facilitating the reduction of silver ions during AgNP synthesis. In addition to serving as a bio-reductant, green tea extract also functions as a natural stabilizing agent for the formed AgNPs (Hermanto *et al.*, 2024).

The present study aimed to green synthesize silver nanoparticles (AgNPs) using aqueous extracts of ginger, garlic, capsicum, green tea leaves, and their combinations, and to evaluate their antimicrobial activity against *Escherichia coli*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Bacillus cereus*, and *Salmonella Typhi*. The most potent AgNP formulation was further incorporated into gelatin based films and carboxymethyl cellulose (CMC) based coatings to assess their effectiveness in enhancing the shelf life and quality of fresh-cut apple, pineapple, and grapes.

2] MATERIALS AND METHODS

Green tea leaves, ginger, garlic, and capsicum were procured from local vendors; silver nitrate (AgNO_3) was purchased from Loba Chemie (India); and laboratory strains of *Escherichia coli*, *Bacillus cereus*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, and *Salmonella Typhi* were obtained from Bhavan's College.

Preparation of aqueous extracts

Fresh plant material (20 g each of ginger rhizome, garlic bulb, green tea leaves, and capsicum) was mixed with 100 mL distilled water, heated at 55 °C for 15 min with stirring, cooled, filtered, and stored at 4 °C in foil-wrapped glass bottles to prevent photodegradation (Reda *et al.*, 2019).

Biosynthesis of AgNPs by using plant extracts

Aqueous plant extracts were used as reducing agents for green synthesis of AgNPs. Individual extracts of ginger, garlic, capsicum, and green tea leaves, as well as their 1:1 combinations, were reacted with AgNO_3 by adding 2 mL of 10 mM AgNO_3 dropwise to 10 mL extract under heating (55 °C) and stirring for 25 min. Formation of AgNPs was indicated by a color change to yellowish brown, and UV–Visible absorbance spectra were recorded between 200–570 nm (Reda *et al.*, 2019).

In vitro antimicrobial activity of AgNPs

Antimicrobial activity was evaluated by agar well diffusion assay against *Escherichia coli*, *Bacillus cereus*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, and *Salmonella Typhi*, common fruit spoilage organisms (Devi *et al.*, 2021). Bacterial suspensions were adjusted to 0.1 OD at 600 nm, swabbed onto nutrient agar plates, and wells (8 mm) were filled with 70 μL of AgNP solutions. Streptomycin (250 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$) and sterile saline served as positive and negative controls, respectively. Plates were incubated at 37 °C for 24 h, and antimicrobial activity was assessed by measuring zones of inhibition (Reda *et al.*, 2019).

Preparation of carboxymethyl cellulose (CMC) based silver nanoparticle coating

Beeswax (1 g) was mixed with olive oil (50 mL), while lecithin (10 g) was dissolved in 200 mL of 0.85% saline and stirred. A 3% CMC solution (150 mL) was added and emulsified, and the volume was adjusted to 1000 mL with 0.85% saline containing 800 ppm sodium hypochlorite (Shah *et al.*, 2015).

The CMC emulsion base was mixed with AgNPs (ginger, garlic, or ginger–capsicum) at 100 µg/mL in a 1:1 ratio to obtain AgNP-incorporated coatings (Shah *et al.*, 2015).

Before coating treatment, fresh cut apple and pineapple fruits were rinsed for 1 minute with distilled water and then stored for 1 hour at room temperature in order to ensure full water evaporation. Fruits were immersed in CMC-Ag coating for 3 minutes. (Shah *et al.*, 2015; Popescu *et al.*, 2022)

Spike testing

Fresh cut apples and pineapples were washed with distilled water and sanitized in 8% sodium hypochlorite for 10 min (Filgueiras *et al.*, 2024). Fruits were inoculated with *Staphylococcus aureus* (10⁴ CFU/mL) by immersion for 2 min, air-dried for 1 h to allow bacterial adhesion, and then coated for 3 min. Samples were stored at room temperature, and microbial load was periodically determined using the Miles and Misra method until visible spoilage occurred (Mehmood *et al.*, 2020).

Weight loss rate (%) (Farina *et al.*, 2020)

$$\text{Weight loss rate (\%)} = \frac{W_i - W_t}{W_t} \times 100$$

Where W_i is the initial weight and W_t is the weight measured during storage

Sensory evaluation (De Bruno *et al.*, 2023)

Sensory analysis was based on perceptions of visual appearance (colour), aroma intensity (fruity, citrus, sweet, fermented), texture (turgidity, juiciness).

Preparation of gelatin nanocomposite films

Gelatin films were prepared by the solution casting method by dissolving 5% gelatin and glycerol (1.5 mL) in 100 mL distilled water with continuous stirring to obtain a homogeneous solution. AgNP solution (1.2 mL, 100 µg/mL) was added dropwise and stirred for 30 min before casting onto Teflon coated sheets, while control films were prepared without AgNPs (Kowsalya *et al.*, 2020).

For microbiological testing, spike testing was carried out as method described by (Mehmood *et al.*, 2020). Sensory properties of grapes during storage was evaluated. Weight loss of grapes during storage was also assessed and was calculated by method described by (Farina *et al.*, 2020)

Film properties

Film thickness

Film thickness was measured using a vernier calliper. For each film sample 3 readings were taken at different positions. (Gudimalla *et al.*, 2021)

Moisture content of film: The moisture content of the films was determined following the protocol described by Azlim *et al.* (2022). The films were cut into 2 × 2 cm sections, and their initial weight (W₁) was recorded. The samples were dried in a hot air oven at 60 °C for 2 hours to ensure complete moisture removal. After drying, the final weight (W₂) of the films were recorded.

$$\text{Moisture content } (\omega) = \frac{W_1 - W_2}{W_1} \times 100$$

Swelling index: The swelling index of the films will be determined gravimetrically following the method described by Taherkhani *et al.*, (2020). Films of 2 × 2 cm will first be dried in a hot air oven at 60 °C for 2 hours, and their initial dry weight (W₁) were recorded. The dried films were immersed in 20 mL of distilled water for 24 hours to allow absorption. After the incubation period, the samples were carefully removed, blotted dry using filter paper to remove excess surface water, and their swollen weight (W₂) was recorded.

$$\text{Swelling index (SI) } (\%) = \frac{W_2 - W_1}{W_1} \times 100$$

3] RESULTS

3.1] Characterization of green synthesized AgNP

Graph 1: UV–Visible absorption spectra of green-synthesized silver nanoparticles (AgNPs)

3.2] Antimicrobial activity – agar well diffusion

Table 1] Mean zones of inhibition against *B.cereus*, *E.coli*, *S.typhi*, *S.aureus* exhibited by different green synthesized AgNPS

AgNP	Mean zone of inhibition			
	<i>Bacillus. cereus</i>	<i>Escherichia. coli</i>	<i>Salmonella. typhimurium</i>	<i>Staphylococcus. aureus</i>
Garlic	18.33 ± 0.57	17.33 ± 0.57	16 ± 0	26.3 ± 0.57
Ginger	22.33 ± 0.57	11.33 ± 0.57	14.33 ± 0.57	16 ± 0
Capsicum	14.66 ± 0.57	14 ± 0	15 ± 0	15.66 ± 0.57
Green tea	20 ± 0	10 ± 0	12.33 ± 0.57	13.66 ± 0.57
Gar-cap	14.66 ± 0.57	15.66 ± 0.57	14.66 ± 0.57	13.66 ± 0.57
Gar-gin	11.33 ± 0.57	14.66 ± 0.57	13 ± 0	13.66 ± 0.57
Gar-tea	19.33 ± 0.57	11 ± 0	14.33 ± 0.57	16.33 ± 0.57
Tea-cap	19.66 ± 0.57	10.66 ± 0.57	13.33 ± 0.57	17.66 ± 0.57
Tea-gin	14.33 ± 0.57	0	12.66 ± 0.57	20.33 ± 0.57
Cap-gin	14 ± 0	15.66 ± 0	15.66 ± 0.57	24.33 ± 0.57
Gar-gin-cap-tea (All)	19 ± 0	13.33 ± 0.57	14.33 ± 0.57	18.33 ± 0.57
PC	25 ± 0	24 ± 0	26 ± 0	29 ± 0

Key: Values are expressed as mean ± SD (n = 3).

Fig 1: Antimicrobial activity against *B.cereus*. 1- PC- Streptomycin, 2- Gar AgNP, 3- NC- St.saline, 4 – garlic extract, 5- capsicum AgNP, 6 – gar-cap AgNP, 7 – gin -tea AgNP, 8 – gin-gar AgNP, 9 – gin-cap AgNP, 10- gin-tea AgNP, 11 – tea AgNP, 12- Ginger AgNP, 13 – all extract AgNP, 14- tea-gar AgNP, 15 – tea-cap AgNP.

Fig 2: Antimicrobial activity against *E.coli*. 1 –gin-gar AgNP, 2-gin-cap AgNP, 3 – garlic AgNP, 4 – PC – Streptomycin, 5- NC – St. saline, 6 – gar-cap AgNP, 7 -cap AgNP, 8 – all extract AgNP, 9 – tea AgNP, 10 – ginger AgNP, 11 – gin-tea AgNP, 12 – ga-tea AgNP, 13 – cap tea AgNP

Fig 3: Antimicrobial activity against *S.typhi*. 1 – gin -gar AgNP, 2 – ginger AgNP, 3 – garlic AgNP, 4 – capsicum AgNP, 5 – tea AgNP, 6 – gar cap AgNP, 7 – gar-tea AgNP, 8 – all extract AgNP, 9 – gin-tea AgNP, 10 – gin-cap AgNP, 11 – tea-cap AgNP, 12 – PC – Streptomycin, 13 – NC – St. saline.

Fig 4: Antimicrobial activity against *S. aureus*. 1 – cap-gar AgNP, 2 – tea AgNP, 3 – garlic AgNP, 4 – capsicum AgNP, 5 – ginger AgNP, 6 – gin -gar AgNP, 7 -tea-gar AgNP, 8 – tea-gin AgNP, 9 – all extract AgNP, 10 – gin-cap AgNP, 11 – tea-cap AgNP, 12 – PC - Streptomycin, 13 -NC -St. saline

Graph 2: Mean zones of inhibition obtained from different AgNP formulations and positive control (Streptomycin 250µg/ml) against *Escherichia. coli*.

Graph 3: Mean zones of inhibition obtained from different AgNP formulations and positive control (Streptomycin 250µg/ml) against *Salmonella. Typhimurium*.

Graph 4: Mean zones of inhibition obtained from different AgNP formulations and positive control (Streptomycin 2500µg/ml) against *Staphylococcus .aureus*

Graph 5: Mean zones of inhibition obtained from different AgNP formulations and positive control (Streptomycin 2500µg/ml) against *Bacillus. Cereus*.

Appearance changes of fresh cut apples during storage coated with prepared coatings

3.3] Effect of CMC based AgNP coatings on fresh cut apple

Fig. 6: A – CMC coating base, B – Garlic AgNP coating, C – gin-cap AgNP coating, D- Ginger AgNP coating.

Fig 7: Appearance changes of fresh cut apples. A- Apple coated with garlic AgNP coating during 4 days of storage at room temperature, B – Apple coated with gin-cap AgNP coating during 4 days storage at room temperature, C- Apple coated with ginger AgNP coating during 4 days storage at room temperature, D – Uncoated apple during storage at room temperature for 4 days, E- Apple coated with CMC coating base.

Weight reduction of apple.

Table 2: Texture, colour, odour of apple during storage of apple.

	Day	Texture	Colour	Odor
Control	0	Firm	White	Sweet
	1	Firm	White	Sweet
	2	Soft	Yellowish brown	Fermented/sour
	3	Very Soft (fungal growth)	Brown	Fermented/sour
	4	Very soft (fungal growth)	Brown	Fermented/sour/rotten
CMC coating	0	Firm	White	Sweet
	1	Firm	White	Sweet
	2	Soft	Brown	Sweet/slightly fermented
	3	Soft	Brown	Fermented/sour
	4	Very soft	Dark brown	Fermented/sour
Garlic AgNP Coating	0	Firm	White	Sweet
	1	Firm	White	Sweet
	2	Slightly soft (from edges, centre firm)	Brown	Sweet
	3	Slightly soft (edges soft, centre firm)	Brown	Sweet and slightly fermented
	4	Soft	Brown	Fermented
Gin-cap AgNP	0	Firm	White	Sweet
	1	Firm	White	Sweet
	2	Firm	Yellow/faint brown	Sweet

	3	Soft	Faint brown	Sweet
	4	Soft	Faint brown	Sweet
Ginger AgNP	0	Firm	White	Sweet
	1	Firm	White	Sweet
	2	Firm	Faint brown	Sweet
	3	Soft	Faint brown	Sweet
	4	Soft	Faint brown	Sweet and slightly fermented

3.4] Spike testing of apple

Fig 8: Effect of AgNP incorporated CMC coatings on bacterial count (\log_{10} CFU/mL) of apple during storage of 4 days.

3.5] Preservative effect of prepared coatings on fresh cut pineapple

Fig 9: Appearance of control pineapple, pineapple coated with CMC coating, coated with garlic AgNP coating, coated with ginger AgNP coating, coated with gin-cap AgNP coating on day 0, 1,2,3,4 of storage at room temperature.

Weight reduction of pineapple

Fig 10: Effect of AgNP incorporated CMC coatings on bacterial count (\log_{10} CFU/mL) of pineapple during storage of 4 days.

Table 3] Texture, colour, odour of pineapple during storage of pineapple.

	Day	Texture	Colour	Odor
Control	0	Firm	Yellow	Sweet
	1	Firm	Yellow	Sweet
	2	Soft	Yellowish brown	Fermented, pungent
	3	Very Soft (squishy)	pale yellow/grey (coat of white layer)	Fermented, pungent
	4	Very soft (squishy)	pale yellow/grey (coat of white layer)	Strong pungent/rotten smell
CMC coating	0	Firm	Yellow	Sweet
	1	Firm	Yellow	Sweet
	2	Soft	Brown	Fermented
	3	Very Soft (squishy)	Pale yellow (appearance of white layer)	Fermented, pungent
	4	Very soft (squishy)	Pale yellow (appearance of white coat)	Rotten, pungent
Garlic AgNP Coating	0	Firm	Yellow	Sweet
	1	Firm	Yellow	Sweet
	2	Soft	Slight brown discolouration	Sweet
	3	Soft	Pale yellow (appearance of white coat)	Sweet, slightly fermented
	4	Soft	Pale yellow (appearance of white coat)	Fermented
Gin-cap AgNP	0	Firm	Yellow	Sweet
	1	Firm	Yellow	Sweet
	2	Firm	Yellow	Sweet
	3	Soft	Yellow (slight brown)	Sweet, slightly

			discoloration from edges)	fermented
	4	Soft	Pale yellow (appearance of white layer)	Sweet, slightly fermented
Ginger AgNP	0	Firm	Yellow	Sweet
	1	Firm	Yellow	Sweet
	2	Soft	Yellow	Sweet, slightly fermented
	3	Soft	Pale yellow (appearance of white layer)	Sweet, slightly fermented
	4	Soft	Pale yellow (appearance of white layer)	Fermented

3.6] Spike testing of pineapple

Fig 3.17] Prepared gelatin and gelatin nanocomposite (garlic AgNP, ginger AgNP, gin-cap AgNP incorporated films) prepared using glycerol as plasticizer.

Fig 11] Prepared gelatin nanocomposite films. A- only gelatin film, B-gelatin-ginger AgNP film, C- gelatin-garlic AgNP film, D- gelatin-gin-cap AgNP film.

3.7] Preservative effect of gelatin nanocomposite film on grapes

Fig 12: Appearance of grapes on day 0,1,2,3,4,5,7 of storage: wrapped with prepared films and unwrapped control.

Graph. :- Weight reduction of grapes**Table 4] Texture, colour, odour of grapes during storage of grapes.**

	Day	Texture	Colour	Odor
Control	0	Firm	Green	Sweet
	1	Firm	Tips slightly brownish	Sweet
	2	Firm	Tips brownish	Sweet
	3	Slightly soft	33% of grapes (5/15) Brown	due to fungal growth)
	4	Slightly soft	40% of grapes (6/15) Brown	due to fungal growth)
	5	due to fungal growth	Brown	due to fungal growth)
	7	due to fungal growth	Brown	due to fungal growth)
Gelatin film	0	Firm	Green	Sweet
	1	Firm	40% of grapes (6/15) appearing slight brownish	Sweet
	2	Firm	46.66% of grapes (7/15) brown	Sweet
	3	Soft	53.33% of grapes (8/15) brown	Sweet
	4	Soft (slightly shrunken)	53.33% of grapes (8/15) brown	Sweet
	5	Soft (slightly shrunken)	60% of grapes (9/15) brown	Sweet and slightly fermented
	7	Soft (shrunken)	73.33% of grapes (11/15) brown	Sweet and slightly fermented
Gelatin - garlic AgNP film	0	Firm	Green	Sweet
	1	Firm	Green	Sweet
	2	Firm	13.33% of grapes (2/15) brown	Sweet
	3	Firm	13.33% of grapes (2/15) brown	Sweet
	4	Soft (slightly	26.66% of grapes (4/15)	Sweet

		shrunken)	brown	
	5	Soft (slightly shrunken)	33.33% of grapes (5/15) brown	Sweet, slight fermented odour
	7	Soft (slightly shrunken)	46.66% of grapes (7/15) brown	Sweet, slight fermented odour
Gelatin - gin-cap AgNP film	0	Firm	Green	Sweet
	1	Firm	Green	Sweet
	2	Firm	Green (tip of 2 grapes starting to turn brown)	Sweet
	3	Firm	13.33% of grapes (2/15) brown	Sweet
	4	Firm	13.33% of grapes (2/15) brown	Sweet
	5	Firm	26.66% of grapes (4/15) brown	Sweet
	7	Soft	33.33% of grapes (5/15) brown	Sweet
Gelatin - ginger AgNP film	0	Firm	Green	Sweet
	1	Firm	Green	Sweet
	2	Firm	Green	Sweet
	3	Firm	Green (tip of 3 grapes turning brown)	Sweet
	4	Firm	13.33% of grapes (2/15) brown	Sweet
	5	Firm	20% of grapes (3/15) brown	Sweet
	7	Slightly soft	20% of grapes (3/15) brown	Sweet

3.8] Spike testing of grapes

Fig 12: Effect of AgNP incorporated gelatin films on bacterial count (\log_{10} CFU/mL) of grapes during storage of 7 days.

3.8] Film properties

Fig 13: Average thickness of prepared films.

Fig 14: Swelling index of prepared films.

Fig 15: Moisture content of prepared films.

Fig 16: FTIR characterization of green synthesized AgNPs using ginger aqueous extract.

3.9] FTIR analysis of synthesized silver nanoparticles

3.10] Particle size analysis

Fig 17: FTIR characterization of AgNPs synthesized using ginger-capsicum aqueous extract.

PARTICLE SIZE ANALYSIS

PARTICLE SIZE ANALYSIS

Measurement Details Sample Name Ginger Capsicum AgNP Company name Laxmi Analytical Laboratories B.No. NM AR No. CAS/PSD/26/02/26/037	Measurement Details Instrument Type Mastersizer3000 Scattering Model Mie Operator Name Admin Analysis Date Time 27-02-2026 10:49:26
Analysis Dispersant Name Water Analysis Model General Purpose (Emulated MS2000 / MS2000E) Particle Absorption Index 0.100 Laser Obscuration 0.73 % Particle Refractive Index 1.520 Weighted Residual 0.12 %	Result D [3,2] 11.0 µm D [4,3] 43.1 µm Dv (5) 5.20 µm Dv (10) 8.52 µm Dv (50) 30.1 µm Dv (90) 84.2 µm Dv (95) 119 µm Dv (97) 162 µm Dv (98) 206 µm Dv (99) 276 µm Dv (100) 504 µm Specific Surface Area 543.5 m ² /kg

Size (µm)	% Volume Under										
0.0200	0.00	0.119	0.00	0.708	1.52	4.22	3.83	25.1	41.69	149	96.60
0.0235	0.00	0.140	0.00	0.833	1.76	4.96	4.70	29.5	49.12	176	97.37
0.0277	0.00	0.165	0.00	0.980	1.94	5.83	5.84	34.7	56.82	207	98.02
0.0325	0.00	0.194	0.00	1.15	2.06	6.86	7.33	40.8	64.47	243	98.59
0.0383	0.00	0.228	0.00	1.36	2.08	8.07	9.25	48.0	71.73	286	99.10
0.0450	0.00	0.268	0.08	1.59	2.08	9.49	11.69	56.5	78.29	336	99.51
0.0529	0.00	0.315	0.22	1.87	2.08	11.2	14.76	66.4	83.87	395	99.80
0.0622	0.00	0.370	0.42	2.20	2.19	13.1	18.55	78.1	88.32	465	99.96
0.0732	0.00	0.436	0.66	2.59	2.39	15.4	23.14	91.8	91.65	547	100.00
0.0861	0.00	0.512	0.95	3.05	2.71	18.1	28.56	108	93.98	643	100.00
0.101	0.00	0.602	1.24	3.59	3.18	21.3	34.77	127	95.54	756	100.00

Fig 18: Particle size of AgNPs synthesized using ginger-capsicum aqueous extract. Particle size was analysed using laser diffraction particle size analyser.

PARTICLE SIZE ANALYSIS

PARTICLE SIZE ANALYSIS

Measurement Details Sample Name Ginger AgNP Company name Laxmi Analytical Laboratories B.No. NM AR No. CAS/PSD/26/02/26/036	Measurement Details Instrument Type Mastersizer3000 Scattering Model Mie Operator Name Admin Analysis Date Time 27-02-2026 10:42:52
Analysis Dispersant Name Water Analysis Model General Purpose (Emulated MS2000 / MS2000E) Particle Absorption Index 0.100 Laser Obscuration 0.95 % Particle Refractive Index 1.520 Weighted Residual 0.21 %	Result D [3,2] 0.397 µm D [4,3] 6.29 µm Dv (5) 0.0886 µm Dv (10) 0.125 µm Dv (50) 2.80 µm Dv (90) 18.0 µm Dv (95) 22.9 µm Dv (97) 26.0 µm Dv (98) 28.2 µm Dv (99) 31.4 µm Dv (100) 38.8 µm Specific Surface Area 15100 m ² /kg

Result											
Size (µm)	% Volume Under										
0.0200	0.00	0.119	9.26	0.708	35.57	4.22	56.07	25.1	96.48	149	100.00
0.0235	0.00	0.140	11.98	0.823	37.07	4.96	58.94	29.5	98.46	176	100.00
0.0277	0.00	0.165	14.83	0.980	38.57	5.83	62.10	34.7	99.65	207	100.00
0.0325	0.00	0.194	17.74	1.15	40.10	6.86	65.58	40.8	100.00	241	100.00
0.0383	0.00	0.228	20.61	1.36	41.70	8.07	69.37	48.0	100.00	286	100.00
0.0450	0.27	0.268	23.35	1.59	43.38	9.49	73.43	56.5	100.00	336	100.00
0.0529	0.80	0.315	25.92	1.87	45.14	11.2	77.68	66.4	100.00	395	100.00
0.0622	1.65	0.370	28.27	2.20	47.00	13.1	82.01	78.1	100.00	465	100.00
0.0732	2.91	0.436	30.39	2.59	48.98	15.4	86.26	91.8	100.00	547	100.00
0.0861	4.65	0.512	32.28	3.05	51.13	18.1	90.33	108	100.00	643	100.00
0.101	6.79	0.602	33.99	3.59	53.48	21.3	93.70	127	100.00	756	100.00

Fig 19: Particle size of AgNPs synthesized using ginger aqueous extract. Particle size was analysed using laser diffraction particle size analyser.

4] DISCUSSION

Silver nanoparticles were effectively synthesized using extracts of ginger, garlic, capsicum, green tea leaves, and their combinations, as evidenced by characteristic surface plasmon resonance (SPR) peaks in UV–Visible spectra. Garlic, garlic–tea, ginger–capsicum, and the combined extract system exhibited SPR maxima around 450 nm, indicating the formation of well-dispersed, predominantly spherical AgNPs with an estimated size range of 30–80 nm,

consistent with efficient phytochemical mediated reduction and stabilization (Vanlalveni *et al.*, 2021; Arumai Selvan *et al.*, 2018).

In contrast, AgNPs synthesized using ginger, capsicum, green tea, garlic–capsicum, garlic–ginger, and tea–ginger showed SPR peaks near 470 nm, suggesting a red shift associated with increased particle size, partial aggregation, or slight deviations from spherical morphology. These nanoparticles are inferred to be spherical to near-spherical, with possible anisotropic features and an estimated size range of 60–80 nm. Variations in SPR peak position and intensity among different extracts are attributed to differences in the nature and concentration of phytochemicals, such as phenolics and flavonoids, which govern nanoparticle nucleation and growth (Vanlalveni *et al.*, 2021).

Notably, AgNPs synthesized using the tea–capsicum extract displayed an SPR peak at 510 nm with an absorbance of 1.87, suggesting the formation of comparatively larger and structurally complex nanoparticles. SPR bands beyond 500 nm are commonly linked to polydisperse systems, enhanced aggregation, or anisotropic morphologies such as triangular nanoplates or nanoprisms, with particle sizes potentially exceeding 100 nm. The marked red shift observed for this extract combination indicates slower reduction rates and less effective stabilization, resulting in increased particle growth and aggregation. Overall, the UV–Visible spectral differences emphasize the significant influence of plant extract composition and phytochemical interactions on the size, morphology, and dispersion of biosynthesized silver nanoparticles (Widatalla *et al.*, 2022; Vanlalveni *et al.*, 2021).

In the present study, garlic extract mediated AgNPs demonstrated the highest antimicrobial activity, producing the largest zones of inhibition against *Escherichia coli*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, and *Salmonella Typhi*. This observation is consistent with previous reports showing strong antibacterial efficacy of garlic based AgNPs, particularly against *E. coli* and *S. aureus* (Mohamed *et al.*, 2021; Abbas *et al.*, 2022). The enhanced activity is attributed to the synergistic action of silver ions and sulfur containing phytochemicals such as allicin, which disrupt bacterial membranes and intracellular components (Shafea *et al.*, 2021). Variations in antimicrobial potency reported among studies may be due to differences in synthesis protocols, extract composition, and nanoparticle size and stability (Sarangi *et al.*, 2024).

Additionally, ginger-mediated AgNPs exhibited a higher zone of inhibition against *Bacillus cereus*, in agreement with earlier studies highlighting the strong antibacterial potential of

ginger-derived nanoparticles against *Bacillus* species (Jassim *et al.*, 2023). This enhanced effect is linked to the presence of gingerols and shogaols, which act as effective reducing and capping agents and synergistically enhance Ag⁺-mediated disruption of bacterial cell membranes and intracellular targets (Ramzan *et al.*, 2024).

Two-way ANOVA analysis further confirmed that the antibacterial activity was significantly influenced by the type of plant extract mediated AgNP formulation ($p < 0.05$). For columns (bacterial species) p value was significantly less than 0.05 (2.14×10^{-43}) which indicates that antimicrobial activity differed significantly among the bacterial species tested. For interaction (AgNP x bacteria) p value was 8.3×10^{-40} , indicating, the effect of treatments on antimicrobial activity varied depending on the bacterial species

Fresh cut apple and pineapple coated with ginger–capsicum (gin–cap) AgNP incorporated coatings showed marked improvement in shelf life during storage. Treated fruits maintained better appearance, texture, and odor than uncoated controls and other treatments, with delayed browning, tissue softening, and off-odor development, indicating reduced enzymatic and microbial spoilage. The enhanced preservation is attributed to the synergistic antimicrobial action of ginger and capsicum phytochemicals with AgNPs, demonstrating the effectiveness of gin–cap AgNP coatings for extending the shelf life of fresh-cut fruits.

Among the gelatin-based films, those incorporated with ginger-mediated AgNPs exhibited the most effective preservation, followed by gin–cap and garlic based AgNP films. AgNP incorporated films showed reduced browning and better retention of texture and appearance compared to plain gelatin films, which displayed pronounced browning and limited protective efficacy. Unwrapped samples showed visible fungal growth from day 3, indicating rapid spoilage, while the improved performance of AgNP films is attributed to enhanced antimicrobial activity and barrier properties that delay enzymatic browning and microbial growth.

The physical properties of gelatin and gelatin–AgNP composite films varied with AgNP incorporation and influenced their barrier performance. Film thickness ranged from 0.20 mm for ginger-AgNP films to 0.36 mm for garlic-AgNP films, with plain gelatin and gin–cap AgNP films showing intermediate values (0.23 and 0.26 mm, respectively). Swelling behavior differed markedly, with ginger-AgNP films showing reduced swelling (200%) compared to plain gelatin (300%), while garlic-AgNP films showed moderate swelling

(225%) and gin–cap AgNP films exhibited the highest swelling (333.3%). Moisture content was lowest in plain gelatin (20%) and increased in AgNP-incorporated films, particularly garlic–AgNP films (50%), followed by gin–cap (33.33%) and ginger–AgNP films (25%).

The FTIR spectrum of ginger mediated AgNPs shows several characteristic absorption peaks indicating the presence of bioactive compounds responsible for reduction and stabilization of silver nanoparticles. A broad absorption band observed at 3275 cm^{-1} corresponds to O–H stretching vibrations of phenols and alcohols, suggesting the presence of polyphenolic compounds responsible for the reduction of silver ions. The peak at 2947 cm^{-1} is attributed to C–H stretching of alkanes, indicating organic constituents from the plant extract. The prominent band at 1640 cm^{-1} corresponds to C=O stretching (amide I), suggesting the presence of proteins or carbonyl groups that may act as capping agents for the nanoparticles. Peaks at 1413 cm^{-1} and 1333 cm^{-1} are associated with O–H bending and C–N stretching vibrations, indicating phenolic compounds and amine groups. The strong peaks at 1111 cm^{-1} and 1041 cm^{-1} correspond to C–O stretching of alcohols, ethers, and carbohydrates, confirming the attachment of plant metabolites to the nanoparticle surface. Additionally, bands observed at 993 cm^{-1} and 919 cm^{-1} may be attributed to C–H bending of aromatic compounds.

The FTIR spectrum of ginger–capsicum mediated AgNPS showed characteristic peaks indicating the involvement of phytochemicals from both extracts in nanoparticle synthesis and stabilization. A broad and intense band observed at 3346 cm^{-1} corresponds to O–H stretching vibrations of phenols and alcohols, suggesting the presence of polyphenolic compounds responsible for the reduction of silver ions. The peak at 1636 cm^{-1} is attributed to C=O stretching (amide I band) or C=C stretching of aromatic compounds, indicating the possible involvement of proteins, flavonoids, or capsaicinoids acting as stabilizing agents on the nanoparticle surface. Strong absorption peaks at 1141 cm^{-1} , 1068 cm^{-1} , and 1003 cm^{-1} correspond to C–O stretching vibrations of alcohols, ethers, and carbohydrates, confirming the presence of plant metabolites attached to the silver nanoparticles. These functional groups suggest that bioactive compounds present in ginger and capsicum extracts played a dual role as reducing as well as capping agents during nanoparticle formation.

The particle size analysis of ginger–capsicum mediated silver nanoparticles was carried out using a Malvern Mastersizer 3000 based on the Mie scattering model. The results revealed a broad particle size distribution with a volume-weighted mean diameter ($D[4,3]$) of $43.1\text{ }\mu\text{m}$

and a surface-weighted mean diameter ($D[3,2]$) of 11.0 μm . The median particle size ($Dv50$) was found to be 30.1 μm , indicating that 50% of the particles were below this size. The $Dv10$ and $Dv90$ values were 8.52 μm and 84.2 μm , respectively, showing a wide distribution range, with 90% of the particles below 84.2 μm . Higher percentile values such as $Dv95$ (119 μm) and $Dv99$ (276 μm) further confirm the presence of larger aggregated particles in the sample.

The frequency distribution graph demonstrates a unimodal but broad peak, suggesting particle agglomeration rather than discrete nanosized particles. Although the nanoparticles were synthesized at the nanoscale, the measured micrometer-sized distribution indicates aggregation of particles in aqueous suspension during analysis. The specific surface area was calculated to be 543.5 m^2/kg , supporting the presence of fine particles with a relatively high surface area. Overall, the analysis indicates that the synthesized silver nanoparticles exhibit a polydisperse and aggregated particle size distribution under the measurement conditions

The particle size analysis of ginger-mediated silver nanoparticles was performed using a Malvern Mastersizer 3000 based on the Mie scattering model. The results showed a volume-weighted mean diameter ($D[4,3]$) of 6.29 μm and a surface-weighted mean diameter ($D[3,2]$) of 0.397 μm . The median particle size ($Dv50$) was 2.80 μm , indicating that 50% of the particles were below this size. The $Dv10$ and $Dv90$ values were 0.125 μm and 18.0 μm , respectively, suggesting that 80% of the particles were distributed between these sizes. Higher percentile values such as $Dv95$ (22.9 μm) and $Dv99$ (31.4 μm) indicate the presence of some larger aggregates within the sample. The particle size distribution graph shows a bimodal pattern, with one population in submicron range and other in microm

The particle size distribution graph shows a bimodal pattern, with one population in the submicron range and another in the micrometer range, suggesting partial aggregation of nanoparticles in suspension. Although silver nanoparticles are expected to be in the nanometer scale, the observed micrometer-sized distribution indicates agglomeration during measurement in aqueous medium. The specific surface area was calculated to be 15100 m^2/kg , reflecting the presence of fine particles with relatively high surface area.

5] CONCLUSION

Silver nanoparticles were green synthesized using extracts of ginger, garlic, capsicum, green tea leaves, and their combinations, as confirmed by characteristic surface plasmon resonance peaks in UV–Visible spectroscopy. Antimicrobial activity varied with the extract used, with

garlic-mediated AgNPs showing strong inhibition against *Escherichia coli*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, and *Salmonella Typhi*, ginger-mediated AgNPs exhibiting selective efficacy against *Bacillus cereus*, and the ginger–capsicum combination demonstrating the highest overall antimicrobial performance. Application of ginger–capsicum AgNP coatings on fresh-cut apple and pineapple effectively preserved visual quality, reduced weight loss, and delayed spoilage during storage. Likewise, AgNP incorporated gelatin films, particularly ginger and ginger capsicum formulations performed better than plain gelatin films by reducing browning, delaying fungal growth, and enhancing barrier properties. Variations in film thickness, swelling, and moisture content further reflected the impact of AgNP incorporation on film functionality, demonstrating the potential of plant-mediated AgNP based coatings and films for sustainable fruit preservation.

6] Future prospects

Future studies may focus on comprehensive physicochemical characterization of the synthesized AgNPs using SEM, TEM, and AAS to elucidate their morphology, particle size distribution, and silver content. Cell cytotoxicity assays (e.g., NRU, MTT, or LDH) should be performed to evaluate the biocompatibility and safety of AgNP incorporated coatings and films for food contact applications. Further assessment of the developed films with respect to mechanical and barrier properties, such as tensile strength, elongation at break, and water vapour permeability, would help establish their suitability for food packaging. Optimization of coating formulations through density and viscosity measurements may enhance coating uniformity and application efficiency. Additionally, testing AgNP based coatings and films on a broader range of fruits and food models, with increased sample size and extended storage studies, would support scalability and practical applicability.

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